

1
2
3 **Conditioned aversion to olive tree leaves (*Olea europaea* L.)**
4 **in goats and sheep**
5

6 Carmen L. Manuelian ^a, Elena Albanell ^{a1}, Ahmed A. K. Salama ^{a,b}, and Gerardo Caja ^a

7 ^a Grup de Recerca en Remugants (G2R), Departament de Ciència Animal i dels

8 Aliments, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Spain

9 ^b Sheep and Goat Research Department, Animal Production Research Institute, 12311

10 Dokki, Giza, Egypt
11
12

13 **ABSTRACT:** With the aim of adverting to olive tree leaves, lithium chloride (LiCl) as
14 used in goats and sheep. A total of 10 dairy does (Murciano–Granadina breed) and 10
15 dairy ewes (Manchega breed) were used in 2 simultaneous experiments for comparing
16 olive leaf intake in averted vs. control animals. Does and ewes were dry and non-
17 pregnant and were randomly allocated into 4 experimental groups of 5 animals each.
18 Animals had no previous contact with olive leaves. For aversion induction, all animals
19 were penned in individual box stalls during 6 d, fed tall fescue hay ad libitum, and
20 offered the olive leaves for 5 min (does) or 1 h (ewes). Aversion was induced by using a
21 drenching gun for orally administering a solution of LiCl (200 mg/kg BW) in water,
22 immediately following olive leaf consumption in the averted groups. Water alone was
23 drenched in the control groups as a blank. Does learned faster to eat the olive leaves and

¹ Corresponding author: elena.albanell@uab.cat

24 developed stronger aversion to the LiCl treatment than ewes. After the aversion
25 induction period, all the animals joined their respective flock or herd, grazed a
26 cultivated pasture during the day and were complemented indoors with tall fescue hay
27 during the night. Aversion memory was evaluated every 14 d via of 5 min lasting 144 d
28 in the does, and 10 min lasting 130 d in the ewes. No LiCl was given during the
29 aversion memory test period. No olive tree leaf consumption was detected until day 53
30 and 23, for does and ewes, respectively ($P < 0.05$). Olive tree leaf consumption in the
31 averted groups was lower than in the control groups throughout the experiment ($P <$
32 0.05). Animal behavior, when the olive leaves were offered, differed between averted
33 and control groups during learning and memory test periods. Animals in the control
34 group avidly ate the olive leaves, whereas animals in the averted groups strongly
35 rejected the olive leaves. In conclusion, the LiCl conditioned aversion to olive tree
36 leaves proved to be an efficient short-term method in sheep and goats under our
37 experimental conditions. The method may be of special interest for implementing
38 selective grazing and for avoiding the use of herbicides in organic cultures. Further
39 research will be necessary before recommending its use in practice.

40

41

INTRODUCTION

42 Diet selection in small ruminant is the result of animal physiological conditions and
43 chemical characteristics of the feeds (Provenza, 1996). Other factors for diet selection
44 are mother, social and environment interactions (Thorhallsdottir et al., 1987; Mirza and
45 Provenza, 1994; Burritt and Provenza, 1997) and aversion experiments (du Toit et al.,
46 1991; Provenza et al., 1994; Provenza, 1995).

47 Discomfort or sickness after eating some particular feed may create an aversive post-
48 ingestive feedback that causes a decrease in intake of that feed. Provenza (1995) points

49 out that learning can be used to condition ruminant feed selection in practice. Intake
50 decrease is the result of organoleptic characteristics (flavor, taste, texture) and post-
51 ingestive effects (Provenza, 1996).

52 The most used drug for conditioning aversion in ruminants is lithium chloride (**LiCl**)
53 (Ralphs and Provenza, 1999; Ralphs et al., 2001), which is a safe (Prien et al., 1971),
54 water-soluble and easy-to-dose product. After administration, LiCl produces
55 indisposition because the emetic system is activated. However, animals recover quickly
56 after LiCl treatment (Burritt y Provenza, 1989; Provenza, 1995). An effective dose of
57 LiCl in sheep and goats ranges between 150 and 200 mg/kg BW (du Toit et al., 1991;
58 Egber et al., 1999). Aversion can persist long term (until 9 mo) and can be re-
59 established with a new dose of LiCl (Burritt and Provenza, 1990; Doran et al., 2009).
60 However, Gorniak et al. (2008) showed that persistence of aversion is related with the
61 possibility of choosing an alternative feed in goats.

62 The aim of this experiment was to study whether LiCl-treated goats and ewes can be
63 averted from consuming olive tree leaves, used as a novel feed, under experimental
64 farm conditions, and to evaluate the persistence of the achieved aversion.

65

66

MATERIALS AND METHODS

67 The experiment was carried out at the Experimental Farm of the SGCE (Servei de
68 Granges i Camps Experimentals) of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Bellaterra,
69 Spain) during spring and early summer (March to July). The experimental procedures
70 and animal care conditions were approved by the Ethical Committee of Animal and
71 Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (reference
72 09CEEAH781).

73 A total of 10 Murciano-Granadina dairy goats (34.7 ± 2.4 kg BW) and 10 Manchega
74 dairy ewes (63.7 ± 3.5 kg BW) were used in 2 simultaneous experiments for comparing
75 olive tree (*Olea europaea* L.) leaf intake in averted vs. control animals. Goats and ewes
76 were dry and non-pregnant, grazed during the day (6 h/d) in an Italian rye-grass (*Lolium*
77 *multiflorum* Lam.) pasture and received fescue hay (*Festuca arundinacea* L.) as a
78 complement in the shelter.

79

80 ***Conditioning Aversion Period***

81 Animals were penned in individual boxes (1.1×2.0 m) and randomly allocated into
82 4 groups of 5 animals each, to which experimental treatments were applied. Treatments
83 consisted of induced aversion (**AV**, LiCl treated) and control (**C**, water blank). All the
84 animals were fed a basal diet of fescue hay ad libitum once a day (1300 h). Water and a
85 commercial block of vitamins and minerals (Multi-Block, Agraria Comarcal del Vallès,
86 Les Franqueses, Barcelona, Spain) were freely available. Visual contact between
87 animals of different treatments was avoided. After 1 wk of adaptation, aversion
88 conditioning was carried out during 6 d. With this aim, basal diet orts were removed
89 (1000 h) and weighed daily. Therefore, animals were individually offered, for 5 min or
90 1 h, in goats or ewes, respectively, 400 g of dry olive leaves. This was the first time the
91 animals had eaten dry olive leaves in their lives (novel feed). Fescue hay and olive leaf
92 composition are shown in Table 1.

93 The olive tree leaves were collected at the end of the olive harvest season (January)
94 in the cooperative “La Palma d’Ebre” (Tarragona, Spain) and belonged to the
95 denomination of origin Siurana oil and corresponding to the cv. Arbequina, which is the
96 most used in Catalonia (NE of Spain). The leaves were air-dried for 1 wk and stored at
97 room temperature until use.

98 Olive leaf intake was measured by weight difference, and animal eating behavior and
99 feed spillage, if occurred, were recorded during the aversion learning period. Animals
100 consuming olive leaves in the aversion group received LiCl (Panreac, Castellar del
101 Vallés, Barcelona, Spain), using a 200 mL drenching gun (Pimex, Abadiño, Vizcaya),
102 immediately after olive leaf ingestion with 0.20 g LiCl/kg BW dissolved in 100 mL of
103 distilled water. Animals in the control groups received 100 mL of water as a blank to
104 simulate the drenching effect. After the learning period, all the animals joined their
105 respective flock or herd, grazed a Italian rye-grass pasture during the day and were
106 complemented with fescue hay in the shelter.

107

108 ***Testing Aversion Memory Period***

109 Aversion memory was evaluated by fortnightly tests of 5 min lasting 144 d in the
110 averted goats and 10 min lasting 130 d in the averted ewes. Test days were: goats (d 22,
111 23, 37, 53, 68, 86, 101, 115, 130 and 144) and ewes (d 23, 24, 42, 58, 72, 87, 101, 116
112 and 130). With this aim, experimental animals were individually restrained in the
113 shelter before grazing (1000 h) using the head-lockers of the feed bunks. Enough space
114 between animals was ensured by leaving empty places to prevent cross consumption.
115 Each animal was offered 400 g of olive leaves in plastic containers (30 × 30 × 15 cm).
116 Intake was measured by weight difference, and animal behavior and feed spillage, if
117 occurred during the test, were recorded. No LiCl was given to animals consuming olive
118 leaves in either treatment during the memory test period.

119

120 ***Statistical Analyses***

121 Intake of olive leaves was analyzed through a mixed model of repeated measures
122 using the PROC MIXED procedure of SAS (SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC; Version 9.1) by

123 specie (goat or sheep). The repeated factor was experimental days. Animals were a
124 random factor nested within treatments. Even though sample sizes were small, the
125 magnitude of the treatment effects was large, the SE small and the mixed model
126 procedure, sufficiently robust to show the treatment effects and the day \times treatment
127 interactions ($P < 0.05$). Significance was declared at $P < 0.05$. When F-ratios were
128 significant, multiple mean comparisons, using the least significant difference (LSD),
129 were used to test for differences between means.

130

131 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

132

133 *Aversion Conditioned Learning in Goats*

134 On the first day of aversion conditioning, there was no difference between the olive
135 leaf intakes of the C and AV goat groups (Table 2). Small ruminants, and especially
136 goats, are neophobic to new feeds (Van Tien et al., 1999; Villalba and Provenza, 2000),
137 which is why the C group ingested increasing amounts of olive leaves on successive
138 days, indicating that goats accepted the new feed. Goats in the AV group rejected
139 consuming olive leaves on the next day after the first LiCl dose (Table 2), although 1
140 goat regurgitated the LiCl and needed a second dose on d 3. Similar results were
141 observed by Barbosa et al. (2008) in goats fed the toxic plant mascagnia (*Mascagnia*
142 *rigida* L.), as novel feed, and in which the aversion was conditioned with 100 mg/kg
143 BW of LiCl. Nevertheless, 28% (2 out of 7) of goats needed a second dose to be
144 effectively averted. Moreover, Gorniak et al. (2008) reported that goats were also
145 averted from consuming leucaena (*Leucaena leucocephala*) with 130 mg LiCl/kg BW,
146 although 30% (2 out of 6) of averted goats needed a second dose.

147 The marked difference in intake between both AV and C goat groups ($P < 0.001$)
148 showed the effectiveness of LiCl to create aversion in goats. At d 6 of the conditioning
149 aversion period all treated goats showed aversion to olive leaves (Figure 1). Goat
150 behavior differed between groups during the offering time of olive leaves. Animals in C
151 group approached the feeding boxes and ate the olive leaves avidly, whereas animals in
152 AV group did not approach the feeding boxes or sniff the olive leaves and rejected
153 them, trying to overturn the plastic containers, which agreed the behavior of averted
154 animals reported by Burritt and Provenza (1989).

155

156 *Aversion Conditioned Memory Test in Goats*

157 Similar aversion behavior was observed in the AV goats until d 53 during the
158 memory test (Figure 1). On that day, the same goat which needed a second LiCl dose on
159 d 3, started to eat olive leaves (16.0 g) and reached 66.0 g on d 144. Until d 53, 80% of
160 AV goats had total aversion to olive leaves and, until d 130, the percentage of animals
161 with total aversion was 40%. A total of three goats ate olive leaves on d 101, and on d
162 144 (end of the memory test study), all the goats ate olive leaves (Figure 1).

163 However, intake differences between AV and C groups (Figure 2) remained
164 significant at the end of the study (d 144), being on average 60.0 ± 5.0 vs. 24.4 ± 12.0 g,
165 for C vs. AV, respectively; $P < 0.05$).

166 The full aversion period was longer than obtained by Barbosa et al. (2008) in goats
167 fed mascagnia, which could be a consequence of the greater dose of LiCl used during
168 the conditioning aversion period in our case.

169

170 *Aversion Conditioned Learning in Ewes*

171 On the first day of aversion conditioning, there was no difference between the olive
172 leave intake of the C and AV ewe groups; and C group ingested increasing amounts of
173 olive leaves on successive days, indicating that they accept olive leaves, as observed in
174 goats (Table 2). Animals in the AV group rejected consuming olive leaves on the next
175 day after the first LiCl dose (Table 2) and none of them needed a new dose of LiCl.

176 Intake difference between C and AV groups was highly significant ($P < 0.001$) and
177 demonstrated the effectiveness of LiCl to create aversion in ewes. At the end of the
178 conditioning aversion experiment (d 6), we observed a total aversion ($P < 0.001$) of the
179 AV ewes to olive leaves (Figure 3). As previously indicated in goats, ewes results were
180 more marked than the ones reported by Burrit and Provenza (1989) with lambs probably
181 for the same dose used reason. The behavior of the averted ewes was similar to that
182 observed in goats.

183

184 *Aversion Conditioned Memory Test in Ewes*

185 Eight days after the conditioning aversion experiment, and before starting the
186 aversion conditioned memory tests, 1 sheep of AV group died by unknown cause. The
187 necropsy done at the Service of Animal Pathology of the Universitat Autònoma de
188 Barcelona did not show lesions associated with LiCl administration or intoxication.

189 During the memory test experiments with ewes, a less marked aversion than in goats
190 was observed (Figure 3). Averted ewes sniffed olive leaves and tried to overturn the
191 containers, or tasted olive leaves but rejected to ingest them. From d 87 to 130, ewes in
192 AV group increased olive leaf consumption, however, difference in intake between C
193 and AV groups was maintained until d 130 (83 ± 14 vs. 40 ± 20 g; $P < 0.05$; Figure 4).
194 Our results agreed with those of Burrit and Provenza (1989) in lambs, in which reported

195 the obtention of a partial aversive behaviour to wheat grain during 2 mo by using LiCl
196 (0.15 mg/kg BW).

197 The increase of the amount of olive leaves consumed by the AV group at the end of
198 the study, indicated that the aversion created to the olive leaf lasted 5 mo at least, and
199 started to be forgotten thereafter. This time is shorter than the 9 mo reported by Burritt
200 and Provenza (1990) and Doran et al. (2009) during pasture trials. The difference
201 between experiments may be a consequence of the experimental conditions used in each
202 case. Thus, in our study, during the aversion memory tests the animals could not choose
203 an alternative feed to olive leaves. It is known that, even the averted animals reduced
204 feed intake compared to control, the extinction of the aversion occurs because there is
205 no negative reinforcement for avoiding the averted feed (Provenza, 1995; Raplths and
206 Provenza, 1999). As reported by Burritt and Provenza (1990) it should be necessary to
207 apply a new dose for re-establish the aversion.

208 In both species, goats and ewes, we observed that averted animals associated their
209 illness to the olive leaf consumption rather than to the act of administering the LiCl dose
210 to them by gun drenching, as reported by Burritt and Provenza (1989). No decrease of
211 olive leaves or fescue hay intake was recorded in C groups of goat and ewes.

212

213 **CONCLUSIONS**

214 The results of this study supported that the feeding behaviour of small ruminants can
215 be manipulated using conditioned feed aversion, which was easily created by using
216 LiCl. The persistence of the effect, for the same dose per kg of BW, was longer in goats
217 than in ewes. In conclusion, aversive conditioning is a easy method for inducing
218 selective grazing of sheep and goat in practice. The method may be of special interest
219 for avoiding the use of herbicides in ecological cultures (e.g. olive and fruit trees,

220 vineyards) and allowing grazing in areas in which specific plants must be respected (i.e.
221 protected and toxic species). Further research will be necessary before recommending
222 its use in practice.

223

224

LITERATURE CITED

225 Barbosa, R. R., I. Pacífico da Silva and B. Soto-Blanco. 2008. Development of
226 conditioned taste aversion to *Mascagnia rigida* in goats. *Pesq. Vet. Bras.* 28:
227 571-574.

228 Burritt, E. A. and F. D. Provenza. 1989. Food aversion learning: ability of lambs to
229 distinguish safe from harmful foods. *J. Anim. Sci.* 67:1732-1739.

230 Burritt, E. A. and F. D. Provenza. 1990. Food aversion learning in sheep: persistence of
231 conditioned taste aversions to palatable shrubs (*Cercocarpus montanus* and
232 *Amelanchier alnifolia*). *J. Anim. Sci.* 68:1003-1007.

233 Burritt, E. A. and F. D. Provenza. 1997. Effect of an unfamiliar location on the
234 consumption of novel and familiar foods by sheep. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.*
235 54:317-325.

236 Doran M. P., M. R. George, J. H. Harper, R. S. Ingram, E. A. Laca, S. Larson and G.T.
237 McGourty. 2009. Vines and ovines: using sheep with a trained aversion to grape
238 leaves for spring vineyard floor management. Page 325 in Proc. 60th Annual
239 Meeting EAAP, Barcelona, Spain.

240 du Toit, J. T., F. D. Provenza and A. S. Nassis. 1991. Conditioned food aversions: how
241 sick a ruminant must get before it detects toxicity in foods?. *Appl. Anim. Behav.*
242 *Sci.* 30:35-47.

243 Egber, A., S. Landau, A. Perevolotsky, A. Shlosberg and M. Belaich. 1999. Using
244 lithium chloride to elicit conditioned feed aversion in ewe-lambs: preliminary
245 results with vetch hay. *Options Méditerranéennes, Séries Cahiers* 39:179-182.

246 Gorniak, S. L., J. A. Pfister, E. C. Lanzonia and E. R. Raspantini. 2008. A note on
247 averting goats to a toxic but palatable plant, *Leucaena leucocephala*. *Appl.*
248 *Anim. Behav. Sci.* 111 :396-401.

249 Mirza, S. N. and F. D. Provenza. 1994. Socially induced food avoidance in lambs: direct
250 or indirect maternal influence?. *J. Anim. Sci.* 72:899-902.

251 Prien, R. F., E. M. Jr. Caffey and C. J. Klett. 1971. Lithium carbonate: a survey of the
252 history and current status of lithium in treating and mood disorders. *Dis. Nerv.*
253 *Syst.* 32:521-531.

254 Provenza, F. D. 1995. Postingestive feedback as an elementary determinant of food
255 preference and intake in ruminants. *J. Range Managem.* 48:2-17.

256 Provenza, F. D. 1996. Acquired aversions as the basis for varied diets of ruminants
257 foraging on rangelands. *J. Anim. Sci.* 74: 2010-2020.

258 Provenza, F. D., J. J. Lynch and J. V. Notan. 1994. Food aversion conditioned in
259 anesthetized sheep. *Physiol. Behav.* 55: 429-432.

260 Ralphs, M. H. and F. D. Provenza. 1999. Conditioned food aversions: principles and
261 practices, with special references to social facilitation. *Proceedings of the*
262 *Nutrition Society* 58:831-820.

263 Ralphs, M. H., F. D. Provenza, J. A. Pfister, D. Graham, D. C. Duff and G. Greathouse.
264 2001. Conditioned food aversion: from theory to practice. *Rangelands* 23:14-18.

265 Thorhallsdottir, A. G., F. D. Provenza and D. F. Balph . 1987. Food aversion learning in
266 lambs with or without a mother: Discrimination, novelty and persistence. *Appl.*
267 *Anim. Behav. Sci.* 18: 327-340.

268

Table 1. Chemical composition of fescue hay and olive leaves (DM basis)

Content, %	Fescue hay	Olive leaf
Dry matter	89.99	82.99
Fat	2.68	5.01
Crude protein	11.73	7.29
Crude fiber	24.42	14.97
Neutral detergent fiber	53.49	36.40
Acid detergent fiber	25.90	22.58
Lignin acid detergent	-	14.63
Ash	12.51	5.43

271 Table 2. Olive leaf intake (g) during conditioning aversion experiment (values
 272 are means \pm SE)

Days	Goats		Ewes	
	Control	Aversion	Control	Aversion
1	28.0 \pm 11.0 ^a	16.0 \pm 2.0 ^a	9.6 \pm 3.6 ^a	24.0 \pm 11.0 ^a
2	48.0 \pm 22.0 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b	8.4 \pm 9.4 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b
3	47.0 \pm 21.0 ^a	2.0 \pm 2.0 ^b	8.0 \pm 4.7 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b
4	54.0 \pm 25.0 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b	33.6 \pm 17.9 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b
5	50.0 \pm 18.0 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b	101.2 \pm 36.6 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b
6	48.0 \pm 14.0 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b	165.6 \pm 23.2 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b

273 ^{ab}Within a row and column in each species, values with different superscripts
 274 differ ($P < 0.001$).

275

276 Figure 1. Olive leaf intake of averted goats during the learning and memory periods (□,
277 goats that did not eat olive leaves; ■, goats that eat olive leaves).

278

279 Figure 2. Amount of olive leaves ingested per goat during the aversion conditioning and
280 testing aversion memory experiment (○, control goats; ●, averted goats; $P < 0.05$).

281

282 Figure 3. Olive leaf intake of averted ewes during the learning and memory periods (□,
283 ewes that did not eat olive leaves; ■, ewes that eat olive leaves).

284

285 Figure 4. Amount of olive leaves ingested per ewe during the aversion conditioning and
286 testing aversion memory experiment (○, control ewes; ●, averted ewes; $P < 0.05$).

287

288

289 **Figure 1**

290

291
292

293

294 **Figure 2**

295

296
297

298

299 **Figure 3**

300

301
302

303

304 **Figure 4**

305

306
307